

Effects of Varying Light Intensities and Temperature Levels on the Growth of *Gracilaria spp.* Under Laboratory Condition

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to evaluate the best combination of light intensities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* Specifically, it aims to determine the significant interaction effect between light intensities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* under laboratory conditions. The Experimental set-up was conducted at College of Fisheries Laboratory and Research Station (CFLRS) in Brgy. Siguel, General Santos City for a period of 60 days. Eighteen (18) 3.5L glass tanks were used as experimental units and was stocked with 3g of *Gracilaria spp.* The study tested for six treatments with varying light intensity and temperature levels. The data were analyzed using two-way ANOVA and comparison between significant difference and interaction were analyzed using post-hoc test (Tukey's HSD). After the experiment, the highest mean body weight of *Gracilaria spp.* was obtained from Treatment III, with recorded value of 4.67g. Meanwhile, results also demonstrated that Treatment III obtained the highest weight gain with 1.67g. Likewise Similarly, Treatment III recorded the highest specific growth rate with 0.32% per day. Statistical analysis revealed that light intensity has a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) and that there is no significant effect ($p > 0.05$) on temperature. On the other hand, there is a significant interaction ($p < 0.05$) between light intensity and temperature on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* (MW, MWG, and SGR) after 60 days of culture. The study concluded that the best growth of *Gracilaria spp.* can be achieved of water at light intensity of 120 m-2 s-1 and temperature 30°C under laboratory condition.

KEYWORDS: : Effects, *Gracilaria spp.*, Growth, Light Intensity, Temperature Levels

INTRODUCTION

Gracilaria is a warm-water seaweed that prefers temperatures between 20 and 30 degrees Celsius. It's an excellent candidate for aquaculture because of its warm-water growth period, ease of multiplication, relatively high growth rates, strong tolerance for a variety of environmental conditions, and present and future economic value (Chamber, et. al., 2019). It played a key part in the manufacture of agar. Agars are now produced from five species in three orders of red algae and commercialized as 'natural agar' in squares or strips or 'industrial agar' in powder form. The development of industrial procedures based on alkaline sulphate hydrolysis has resulted in the manufacture of high-quality food agar from *Gracilaria*. According to Yang, et. al. (2015), light, temperature, salinity, nutrients, cultivation depth, water movement, and herbivorous fish and epiphytes are all factors to consider.

Seawater media (seawater and nutrients), temperature, and light are the three most essential parts of a culture system. However, the marine environment is characterized by changing temperatures, light intensities, and salinities. A strain can be chosen by evaluating its responsiveness to various abiotic variables. Light is required for photosynthesis in both seaweed and higher plants because it is utilized to absorb nutrients, particularly nitrogen and carbon, into cells. Algae can produce a variety of metabolic changes to adapt to shifting light regimes and water temperatures. Temperature has a considerable impact on the growth rate of *Gracilaria* spp. This study aims to evaluate the best combination of light intensities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp.

Literature Review

Gracilaria typically grows on sandy or muddy sediments protected from waves in the eulittoral zone or just below it at the beginning of the sublittoral zone. It can sometimes be seen free-floating in salt or brackish water tidal lakes. It can adapt to large changes in growing conditions such as freshwater dilution, fertilizer concentration increases from runoff, and increased temperatures (Qin, 2018). *Gracilaria* spp. cylindrical's filamentous thalli are around 1 to 2 millimeters in diameter, generally purple-red, but rarely yellow-brown, and can develop to be fairly long, up to 5 meters in length (Tabet, 2013).

In this regard, FAO (2011) explained that *Gracilaria* will cease growing if the temperature rises over 30°C or falls below 10°C, and will rot and die if the temperature rises beyond 35°C. The photosynthetic and respiratory responses of *Gracilaria parvispora* from the southeast Gulf of California were investigated at four different temperatures (20, 25, 30, 35 °C) and salinity (25, 30, 35, 40 psu). *G. Parvispora* was shown to be sensitive to low salinities (25 ppt) and low temperatures (20 °C) (Orduña, et.al., 2013).

To regulate photoperiod, attach lights to an interval timer. Photoperiod is the alternating period of light and dark, which is critical for normal seaweed development and growth. A neutral photoperiod, consisting of 12 hours of light followed by 12 hours of darkness, is often utilized (12:12, L:D) (Kim, et.al, 2012). Light limitation is a major element influencing seaweed development (Xiao, et.al, 2019). LEDs generate monochromatic light in an energy-efficient manner, implying that they might be used to complement light for seaweed development (Kim, et.al, 2015). Under proper LED light settings, seaweed growth rate might be enhanced by 10-60% as compared to fluorescent light culturing (Schulze et al. 2016). Despite the fact that LED lighting has been offered as a light source for *Gracilaria* production (Kim, et.al, 2015). *Gracilaria* spp. is a marine benthic green alga that is extremely light sensitive. Light intensity reportedly has a significant effect on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp, a type of seaweed adapted to a low light intensity of 10 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, and that it could improve light tolerance in different ways under high light intensities of 120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 360 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, but light intensity of 360 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for up to 12 h could cause photo-oxidation and damage. (Huang, et al. 2017) *Gracilaria tenuistipitata* tolerated a wide range of light intensities from 100–700 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site and Facilities

The research was conducted at the College of Fisheries Laboratory and Research Station, Mindanao State University (CFLRS-MSU) in Brgy. Siguel, General Santos City (Fig. 1), where adequate equipment and appropriate facilities was provided for the culture period of 60 days.

Figure 1. Location Map of the Study Area

Experimental Design and Treatments

This study used Complete Randomized Design (CRD) in 2x3x3 factorial. There are six (6) treatments that are used for this study, consisting combinations of two (2) for light intensities and three (3) temperature levels, each treatment was replicated three (3) times. Treatments will be as follows:

Treatment	Light Intensity + Temperature
I	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 20°C
II	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 25°C
III	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 30°C
IV	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 20°C
V	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 25°C
VI	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ + 30°C

Experimental Set-up

A total of eighteen transparent glass tanks with the size of 6x6x8 with 3.5L capacity was used as culture containers in the study. The glass tanks were put on a black covered culture shelf and labeled with the light intensity and temperatures allotted to the treatments and replicates. Each glass tank contained 2.5L of seawater, LED tube was installed to obtain the desired light intensity needed by the study, lux meter was used to measure light intensity; and a thermostat was used to adjust temperature in order to achieve and maintain the desired temperature. The experiment took place inside the facility, with continual aeration and illumination (Fig II). Lux meter was calibrated using regular calibration with controlled light set up and ice water method were used (0°C/32°F) for Thermometer. Temperature Fluctuation were encountered during change water.

Figure 2. Experimental Set Up

Aquarium Preparation

Sterilization of culture media was done before the experiment started. Each glass tank was washed with dish washing soap and leached before used, filled the tank with distilled water, allowed to sit before rinsing for use. The collected seawater was filtered by net. All glass tanks were sealed to prevent contamination, kept in a cool dark place to prevent growth of unwanted algae and set for several days before using or being aerated.

Experimental Species and Conditioning

Gracilaria spp. was provided by Bula Seaweed Farmers Association in cooperation with the BFAR Region XII. The selected healthy thalli of *Gracilaria spp.* were washed many times with filtered saltwater to eliminate debris, zooplankton, and phytoplankton. The seedlings were conditioned in glass tanks for a week. To acclimate samples to experimental treatments, seaweeds was assigned into glass tanks. The water was increased at the rate of 5°C every two days up to 20°C, 25°C, and 30°C respectively and the light intensity was increased by 40 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ everyday up to 120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The experiment started after reaching the desired temperature level and light intensity (Fig 3.).

Figure 3. Experimental Species and Conditioning.

Fertilization and Fertilizer Management

A day before the experiment, fertilization was done using 0.02 grams of ammonium phosphate and it has proven effective to give cultures with nutrients via pulse feeding at the right frequencies and concentrations. The application of Fertilizer was done only at night and at intervals of 3 days.

Stocking and Stock Management

After the selection of *Gracilaria spp.* upright branches was cut with scissors, weigh 3g and rinse with filtered seawater. The 3g thalli of *Gracilaria spp.* was placed in 3.5L glass tanks with 2.5L of filtered seawater and with continual aeration observed. Light Intensity installed using LED lights on the top of the glass tanks and temperature was controlled using thermostats to achieve and maintained the desired temperature. The initial weight of the algae was measured at the start of the experiment by using digital weighing scale. Each sample weight was recorded after fifteen days and the culture media was changed after sampling (Fig 4.).

Figure 4. Measurement of Initial Weight and Stocking of *Gracilaria spp.*

Water Management

Temperature, salinity, and pH of the water was measured using thermometer, refractometer, and pH meter. This was checked twice on a daily basis around eight o'clock (8:00 am) in the morning and three o'clock (3:00 pm) in the afternoon. Seawater was changed three times a week to maintain its good condition.

Data Analysis

The effects on its growth were evaluated by computing the growth parameters using the following formulas.

$$(1) \text{ Mean Weight (g) } = \frac{\text{Total Weight of Seaweeds}}{\text{No. of Seaweeds Sampled}}$$

$$(2) \text{ Mean Weight Gain (g) } = W_2 - W_1$$

Where:

W_2 = Final weight

W_1 = Initial weight

$$(3) \text{ Specific Growth Rate (\%)} = \frac{\log(w_t) - \log(w_i)}{t} \times 100$$

Where:

SGR = specific growth rate (% in wet weight per day)

W_t = weight after t days

W_i = initial weight

t = time in day

(4) Recovery Rate (%)

$$RR(\%) = \frac{\text{no. of species recovered}}{\text{Total no. of species}} \times 100$$

Statistical Analysis

Two-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the level of significance on mean body weight, mean weight gain and specific growth rate of *Gracilaria spp.* Post-hoc test (Tukey’s HSD) was used to compare the multiple significant interaction, and SPSS version 20 was used to analyze all statistical data since all treatments had the same results for survival rate.

Results and Discussion

The results of the effects of varying light intensities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* are shown in Table 1. Statistical analysis revealed that there is a significant interaction ($p < 0.05$) between light intensity and temperature on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* after 60 days of culture.

Table 1. Growth Parameters of *Gracilaria spp.* after 60 days of culture

Treatment	Light Intensity	Temperature	Mean Weight (MW), g	Mean Weight Gain (MWG), g	Specific Growth Rate (SGR), %/day	Survival Rate (%) ^{ns}
I	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	20 °C	4.53±0.12*	1.53±0.12*	0.30±0.19*	100.00
II		25 °C	4.50±0.10*	1.50±0.10*	0.29±0.02*	100.00
III		30 °C	4.67±0.06*	1.67±0.06*	0.32±0.01*	100.00
IV	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	20 °C	3.80±0.10*	0.80±0.10*	0.17±0.02*	100.00
V		25 °C	4.00±0.10*	1.00±0.10*	0.21±0.02*	100.00
VI		30 °C	3.77±0.06*	0.77±0.06*	0.16±0.01*	100.00

(*) Values are significantly different with each other ($p < 0.05$).

The growth performance of *Gracilaria spp.* generally exhibited an increasing growth trend, as shown in Figures V-VII. From an initial body weight of 3 grams in all treatments, the highest mean body weight of *Gracilaria spp.* was obtained from Treatment III (120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 30^\circ\text{C}$), followed by Treatment I (120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 20^\circ\text{C}$), II (120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 25^\circ\text{C}$), V (220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 25^\circ\text{C}$), IV (220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 20^\circ\text{C}$) and VI (220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 30^\circ\text{C}$) with recorded values of 4.67g, 4.53g, 4.50g, 4.00 g, 3.80 g, and 3.77g respectively (Fig V.).

Figure 5. Mean Weight (g) of *Gracilaria spp.* under Laboratory Condition after 60 Days of Culture

Results also demonstrated that Treatment III obtained the highest weight gain with 1.67g, followed by Treatment I with 1.53g, Treatment II with 1.50g, Treatment V with 1.00g, Treatment 4 with 0.80g and the lowest in Treatment VI with 0.77g (Fig. VI). Similarly, Treatment III recorded the highest specific growth rate with 0.32% per day, followed by Treatment I with 0.30% per day, Treatment II with 0.29% per day, Treatment V with 0.21% per day, Treatment IV with 0.17% per day and the lowest in Treatment VI with 0.16% per day (Fig. VII).

Statistical analysis revealed that light intensity has a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) and that there is no significant effect ($p > 0.05$) on temperature. On the other hand, there is a significant interaction ($p < 0.05$) between light intensity and temperature.

Generally, results revealed that Treatment III ($120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 30^\circ\text{C}$) obtained the best growth. This indicates that regardless of the temperature, MW, MWG and SGR is significantly higher if the light intensity is at $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The result of this study was supported by Macchiavello et.al., (2007) where it was found out that after four weeks of experimental period, *Gracilaria spp.* can tolerate light intensities of 15-91 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and temperature of 13.5-31.1°C.

Figure 6. Mean Weight Gain (g) of *Gracilaria spp.* under Laboratory Condition after 60 days of Culture

Figure 7. Specific Growth Rate (%/day) of *Gracilaria spp.* under Laboratory Condition after 60 Days

Also, it was further stated that there was a clear interaction effect between light intensity and temperature on growth performance of the five *Gracilaria spp.* Moreover, Yu, et.al., (2012) enunciated that *Gracilaria*

edulis grew well at $100 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ while *Gracilaria tenuistipitata var liui* grew well at $60\text{-}130 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and in contrast, reduced growth rate was observed in tolerating $200 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ light intensity.

In addition, Huang et.al (2017), found out that light intensity has a significant effect on the growth of *Gracilaria spp.* and can adapt to a low light intensity of $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $360 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, but light intensity of $360 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for up to 12 h could cause photo-oxidation and damage. *Gracilaria cornea* responded optimally to light intensities between $100\text{-}800 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for growth and photo inhibition occurred above $1000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (Bunsom et.al., 2012). On the other hand, FAO (2011) stated that *Gracilaria spp.* will cease growing if the temperature rises over 30°C or falls below 10°C , and will rot and die if the temperature rises beyond 35°C . The photosynthetic and respiratory responses of *Gracilaria parvispora* from the southeast Gulf of California were investigated at four different temperatures (20, 25, 30, 35°C). *G. parvispora* was shown to be sensitive to low salinities (25 ppt) and low temperatures (20°C) (Orduña et al., 2013).

This study was further supported by Mendes et al. (2012) where it was suggested that the suitable light intensities for laboratory condition of *Gracilaria spp.* can be obtained in $74 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ to $109.2 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Charan et al., (2017) found out that the highest growth rate of *G. blodgettii* was reached at 30°C and noted that it has greater tolerance to high temperature. Likewise, Chen et al., (2021) revealed that greater growth rate of *G. blodgettii* were observed at the higher temperature (30°C). Also, Choi et al. (2006) noted that the highest specific growth rate of *Gracilaria spp.* was obtained at 30°C . During the culture period, *G. verrucosa* grew faster than *G. chorda* and their maximum specific growth rates were $4.95\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ at 30°C (Rebecca et al., 2012).

In contrast, the results indicated that water temperatures of 20°C and 35°C is not suitable for the culture of *Gracilaria spp.* Kumari (2014) also noted that the lowest daily growth rate was recorded for the temperature of 20°C and the salinity of 40 ppt. Further, it was indicated that *Gracilaria crassa* cultured in 35 ppt salinity and at 20°C in temperature demonstrated the lowest growth rate. Also, *G.vermiculophylla* had a low overall growth in 20°C and 24°C since the optimal temperature for the species is at $27\text{-}30^\circ\text{C}$ (Yang et al., 2006).

The recovery rate of *Gracilaria spp.* grown at varying light intensities and temperature levels under laboratory condition recorded 100%, meaning all species were recovered and there is a positive effect on its growth. This was supported by the study of Figueroa et al. (2012) wherein in water temperatures of 15°C , 25°C , and 35°C , all of *G. vermiculophylla* acquired the highest recovered species than *K. alvarezii*. laboratory condition recorded 100%, meaning all species were recovered and there is a positive effect on its growth. This was supported by the study of Figueroa et al. (2012) wherein in water temperatures of 15°C , 25°C , and 35°C , all of *G. vermiculophylla* acquired the highest.

Table 2. Results on Descriptive Statistics on Mean Weight Gain of *Gracilaria spp*

Descriptive Statistics				
Dependent Variable: MWG				
Temperature	Light Intensity	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
20°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.5333	.11547	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.8000	.10000	3
	Total	1.1667	.41312	6
25°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.5000	.10000	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.0000	.10000	3
	Total	1.2500	.28810	6
30°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.6667	.05774	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.7667	.05774	3
	Total	1.2167	.49565	6
Total	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.5667	.11180	9
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.8556	.13333	9
	Total	1.2111	.38484	18

Table 3. Results on Estimated Marginal Mean of Mean Weight Gain of *Gracilaria spp.* under varying light intensities and temperature levels

Light Intensity*Temperature					
Dependent Variable: MWG					
Temperature	Light Intensity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
20°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.533	.053	1.418	1.648
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.800	.053	.685	.915
25°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.500	.053	1.385	1.615
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.000	.053	.885	1.115
30°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.667	.053	1.552	1.782
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.767	.053	.652	.882

Table 4. Results on Descriptive Statistics on Specific Growth Rate of *Gracilaria* spp.

Descriptive Statistics				
Dependent Variable: SGR				
Temperature	Light Intensity	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
20°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.298667	.0185907	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.170933	.0190505	3
	Total	.234800	.0719594	6
25°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.293367	.0161004	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.208067	.0181004	3
	Total	.250717	.0491687	6
30°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.319800	.0090067	3
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.164667	.0111429	3
	Total	.242233	.0854518	6
Total	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.303944	.0178373	9
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.181222	.0248272	9
	Total	.242583	.0665316	18

Table 5. Results on Estimated Marginal Mean of Specific Growth Rate of *Gracilaria* spp. under varying light intensities and temperature levels.

Light Intensity*Temperature					
Dependent Variable: SGR					
Temperature	Light Intensity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
20°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.299	.009	.279	.319
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.171	.009	.151	.191
25°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.293	.009	.273	.313
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.208	.009	.188	.228
30°C	120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.320	.009	.300	.340
	220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.165	.009	.145	.185

CONCLUSIONS

This study was conducted to determine the effects of varying light intensities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp. In the present study, statistical analysis revealed that there is a significant interaction effect ($p < 0.05$) between light intensity and temperature on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp.

The results of the study revealed that the highest mean body weight of *Gracilaria* spp. was obtained from Treatment III ($120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 30^\circ\text{C}$), followed by Treatment I ($120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 20^\circ\text{C}$), II ($120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 25^\circ\text{C}$), V ($220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 25^\circ\text{C}$), IV ($220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 20^\circ\text{C}$) and VI ($220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} + 30^\circ\text{C}$) with recorded values of 4.67g, 4.53g, 4.50g, 4.00 g, 3.80 g, and 3.77g respectively. Meanwhile, results also demonstrated that Treatment III obtained the highest weight gain with 1.67g, followed by Treatment I with 1.53g, Treatment II with 1.50g, Treatment V with 1.00g, Treatment IV with 0.80g and the lowest in Treatment VI with 0.77g. Similarly, Treatment III recorded the highest specific growth rate with 0.32% per day, followed by Treatment I with 0.30% per day, Treatment II with 0.29% per day, Treatment V with 0.21% per day, Treatment IV with 0.17% per day and the lowest in Treatment VI with 0.16% per day.

Statistical analysis revealed that light intensity has a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) and that there is no significant effect ($p > 0.05$) on temperature. On the other hand, there is a significant interaction ($p < 0.05$) between light intensity and temperature on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp. (MW, MWG, and SGR) after 60 days of culture. This indicates that MW, MWG, SGR is significantly higher regardless of the temperature, if the light intensity is exposed to $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Furthermore, the recovery rate of *Gracilaria* spp. grown at varying light intensities and temperature levels under laboratory condition obtained 100%. The recorded water parameters during the culture period are 25-30ppt for salinity levels, $20-30^\circ\text{C}$ for temperatures and 7.45-7.77 for pH. Thus, the study concluded that the best growth of *Gracilaria* spp. can be achieved at light intensity of $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and temperature 30°C under laboratory condition.

It is recommended to conduct a 3x3 factorial study combination of varying low light intensities, salinities and temperature levels on the growth of *Gracilaria* spp. under laboratory condition. It is further recommended to upscale the experiment by using larger containers. Finally, it is recommended to conduct studies on the effect of different fertilizers on the growth and recovery rate of *Gracilaria* spp.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This paper declares no conflict of interest

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